

Tendencias in reports regarding intoxication related with suicidal behavior during 2019 to 2024 in Colombia

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Abstract

Background: Suicide is one of the main causes of death in recent years, and suicidal conduct is a growing public health issue, establishing the necessity to characterize and report how these patients self-harm through intoxication.

Objectives: To describe and analyze the current data regarding the characterization, epidemiological profile and methodologies used in suicidal patients that self-harm through intoxication, as well as establish possible risk factors for this type of practices, identify limitations in the data of the case reports and thus, guide strategies that prevent fatal or adverse health outcomes through an observational descriptive study with the analysis of secondary data.

Methodology: We conducted an analytical and retrospective study based on secondary data analysis. The database was provided by Cisproquim, integrating records of suicide attempts by poisoning from 2019 to 2024. All statistical analysis was performed using R Studio.

Results: Young adulthood is the most affected population group. There is an intrinsic relation between sex and the severity of the case, stating a preponderance of women attempting suicide through intoxication. Most of the cases were registered in urban zones. Antioquia is the department hosting most of the cases. Acetaminophen was the most frequently used medication for suicidal purposes.

Conclusion: Our study allowed us to identify multiple risk factors related to suicide attempts through intoxication and the multiple areas of action available to establish routes to prevent, diagnose and timely treat suicidal ideation and suicide attempts.

Keywords (MeSH): Suicide, suicide attempts, intoxication, poisoning, self-inflicted injury, risk factors, epidemiology

Data sources: The Colombian Security Council (Consejo Colombiano de Seguridad or CCS) database regarding cases of intoxication related with suicidal behavior was used, along with a systematic search conducted in PubMed, EMBASE, Cochrane, and grey literature from ProQuest Dissertations and Theses Global. *The PRISMA-S protocol guided the search strategy.*

Study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions: Data that includes adult population over 18 years, residing in Colombia, in clinical settings of intoxication intended to be suicidal, from 2019 to 2024, encompassing various study designs. Exclusions comprised cases of intoxication classified as accidental, occupational iatrogenic or homicidal, along with cases lacking the minimum variables required for analysis.

Study Appraisal and Synthesis Methods: Data were charted in Excel and synthesized narratively and in summary tables.

Introduction

According to the World Health Organization, approximately 727.000 people take their own life every year, and many others make the attempt. Suicide is the third leading cause of death among 15 to 29-year-olds in 2021 in the world and the rate was 2.2 higher in men than women; low- and middle-income countries were the most affected (73%) (1). In Colombia, a linear upward trend in suicides has been evidenced along the past 10 years, achieving the highest rate in 2023 (6.59 per 100.000 inhabitants). Poisoning was the second leading cause of suicide, just under asphyxia (2); this marks the importance of a study and analysis of suicidal attempts with this method.

It is imperative for the purpose of this article to distinguish the difference between the concepts of suicide and suicide attempt. Suicide is the act of deliberately taking one's own life, while a suicide attempt refers to any non/fatal suicidal behavior that may have been manifested with or without the intention of taking one's own life (3).

Now, as it was mentioned before, attempted suicide through intoxication is a growing public health issue, according to SIVIGILA reporting a total of 24.711 cases of acute chemical poisoning associated with suicidal intent in Colombia during 2022, where 74,2% of the cases were caused by medication poisoning, followed by pesticides (4).

There are multiple risk factors associated with this psychosocial phenomenon, including sex, where women are more likely to use less aggressive and slower methods, such as poisoning, while men prefer potentially lethal methods, such as hanging or shooting (5) being this associated with other risk factors related to social stressors, such as unemployment or marital conflicts (6). Another variable to consider is low educational level, associated with a higher risk of later suicide attempt (7) and substance dependence, where attempters were tallied to predominantly alcohol and sedative hypnotics (8). Nonetheless, depression, the most prevalent mental disease in Colombia, affecting 4.7% of the population (9), is one of the most relevant risk factors, giving patients a likelihood 20 times higher of dying prematurely from suicide, and involving not only a combination of multiple psychological stressors, but also a functional deficiency of the brain monoaminergic transmitters (10). Although suicide is a difficult

challenge, it is preventable (11). We therefore found it necessary to conduct research aimed at developing tools for prevention, enabling early detection of underlying causes of suicide attempts, reducing progression of risk factors, and ensuring timely intervention in clinical settings to prevent fatal outcomes. Accordingly, the objective of this article is to describe the characterization, epidemiological profile and methods used in suicide attempts with poisoning in Colombia during the period of 2019 to 2024 through secondary data analysis while also establishing possible risk factors and promote the development of strategies that prevent deadly consequences.

Methodology

We conducted an analytical and retrospective study based on secondary data analysis (12), where our main objective was to identify and characterize trends in reports of poisoning with suicidal intent in Colombia between 2019 and 2024.

The data was provided by the Chemical Safety Information and Records Center (Centro de Información en Seguridad y Registros Químicos or Cisproquim) database, administered by the Colombian Security Council (Consejo Colombiano de Seguridad or CCS), an entity responsible for collecting, recording and monitoring cases of poisoning and related events nationwide (13). All the information was anonymized.

For this research, records corresponding to the period from January 1st, 2019, to December 31st of 2024 were consolidated and analyzed through a descriptive statistical approach, aiming to determine the prevalence and trends of suicide attempts by poisoning during the study period. The analysis focused on the frequency, distribution, and temporal pattern of cases.

Data was selected and categorized according to the variables provided in the database (table 1), where the inclusion criteria were anonymous case records notified by telephone call to Cisproquim, including people of all ages, residing in Colombia, who presented with intoxication where the intent was classified as suicidal, with any substance, excluding duplicate cases, records lacking the minimum required variables for analysis, and intoxication cases reported with a different intention or cause (accidental, occupational, criminal or homicidal).

Information available in exhibit 1, including sociodemographic variables (age, sex, region of residence), epidemiological variables (year, type of substance involved, route of administration, severity and outcome of the event), and variables related to the surveillance process, such as the time lapse between the event and the case report, were analyzed.

All statistical analysis were performed using R studio (14), and were extrapolated to box-plot graphics regarding the following relations: severity of cases by age, number of cases over the years, severity of the cases by age and sex, severity and number of cases

by geographical zone, distribution of cases by sex, age, and severity, and time of case report via phone call according to primary attention care facility or origin of call.

Our hypothesis were:

- Hypothesis (H1): The highest concentration of cases of intoxication will occur among adolescents and young adults (15-29 years), as this group is particularly vulnerable to psychiatric comorbidities, and easier access to medications (15,16).
- Hypothesis (H2): The most frequently involved substances will be analgesics (acetaminophen, NSAIDs) and psychiatric medications (antidepressants, benzodiazepines, antipsychotics), reflecting their availability and prescription patterns (17,18).
- Hypothesis (H3): Periods of increased social isolation and loneliness, particularly during COVID-19 pandemic (2020-2021), are expected to coincide with higher number of reported suicides attempts by medication poisoning (19).

In accordance with Colombian Law 8030 of 1993, this study did not involve any intervention and was thus classified as a no-risk investigation, exempting it from the requirement for ethics committee approval.

Results

Cases by date

The number of attempted suicides by poisoning per year between 2019 and 2024 was illustrated using a line graph, which reported a total of 20,170 cases during the period described above. The starting point for the data was taken as 2019 (2,457 cases), followed by the lowest number of reported cases in 2020 (2,194 cases), with an exponential increase in 2021 (3,079 cases), reaching its peak between 2022 (4,292 cases) and 2023 (4,658 cases) and finally experiencing a significant decline by 2024 (3,490).

Figure 1 Number of cases by Date

Source: Author's own elaboration

Years, Sex and Severity

The relationship between age, sex, and severity of suicide attempts by poisoning was illustrated using a Boxplot. Both groups showed values that tended toward adolescents and young adults, excluding the group of fatal cases, which had a reported predilection for older ages, such as late adulthood or even old age. The median age was higher in men (21 years) compared to women (19 years), with a moderate interquartile range (IQR: 12-13) in cases of mild poisoning. Continuing with the report of moderate cases of poisoning, a very similar pattern was observed in the median age of the mild cases group, where the median was higher in men (22 years) compared to women (19 years), with a concentrated interquartile range (IQR 12-13). Severe cases of attempted suicide by poisoning showed similar behavior to the previous groups, with a median age that was higher in the group of men (23.35 years) than in the group of women (20 years), with an interquartile range (IQR 15-17) with greater data dispersion and affecting a wider age range, especially in men. Finally, fatal cases showed atypical behavior compared to the previous groups, with

a tendency toward older ages, where only the median of the women's group is shown (41.5 years) with a wide interquartile range in age (IQR 25.5).

Figure 2 Age (years), Sex and severity

Source: Author's own elaboration

Zone vs Severity

The number of cases of attempted suicide by poisoning according to their severity and geographical distribution (rural vs. urban) was represented using a grouped bar chart (Figure 3). Initially, the null hypothesis (H0) proposed that the area did not influence the number of reported cases. However, after grouping the data, a large predominance of reported cases was found in urban areas compared to rural areas, regardless of severity (Table 1). The Chi-square test of independence was applied, yielding a chi-square value of 6.0673 with 3 degrees of freedom ($p=0.184$). Since p was greater than 0.05, the null hypothesis was not rejected. An attempt was made to apply Fisher's test as an alternative, but this was not possible due to the large size of the grouped table.

Figure 3 Zone vs Severity

Source: Author's own elaboration

Table 1 Number of cases in rural and urban areas

Zone	Severity	Number of cases
Rural	Mild	405
	Moderate	619
	Severe	118
Urban	Mild	6238
	Moderate	10991
	Severe	1769

	Fatal	2

Source: Author's own elaboration

Severity by sex

The severity surrounding the gender of the reported cases is shown using a grouped bar chart comparing the number of men and women per case (Figure 3). Initially, the null hypothesis (H0) proposed that there was no relationship between gender and the severity of the poisoning case. However, after grouping the data, a predominance of reported cases was found regardless of severity in the group of women compared to that of men (Table 2). The Chi-square test of independence was applied, yielding a chi-square of 96.759 with 3 degrees of freedom ($p=2.2e-16$). Since p was less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference, the null hypothesis was rejected, and it was established that there is a relationship between sex and the severity of poisoning in each case. An attempt was made to apply Fisher's test as an alternative, but this was not possible due to the large size of the grouped table.

Figure 4 Severity by sex

Source: Author's own elaboration

Table 2 Number of cases by severity and sex

Sex	Fatal	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Female	2	5034	8449	1217
Male	0	1604	3152	669

Source: Author's own elaboration

Distribution of Reporting Time by Call Source

The analysis of reporting times by call origin revealed notable differences across groups. For *Response Agency*, all values were identical (0.87 hours), with an interquartile range (IQR) of 0.000, indicating complete homogeneity and the absence of variability. In contrast, the *others* group showed a median reporting time of 3.85 hours and an IQR of 7.23 hours, reflecting substantial variability; the maximum value reached 13.5 hours, suggesting that some cases experienced considerable delays. Similarly, the *Individual* group presented a median of 2.03 hours (IQR = 6.03), with a maximum of 48.78 hours, evidencing wide dispersion and the presence of extreme values that may reflect differences in access or responsiveness. The *Medical Care Unit* group demonstrated a median of 3.07 hours and an IQR of 6.65 hours, with a maximum of 59.78 hours, also indicating significant delays in some cases despite a relatively low first quartile (1.17 hours). Overall, the *Others*, *Individual*, and *Medical Care Unit* groups displayed high variability in reporting times with markedly elevated maximum values, whereas *Response Agency* was characterized by complete uniformity. These findings suggest potential disparities in efficiency, accessibility, and case management depending on the origin of the call.

Figure 5 Distribution of Reporting Time (in Decimal Hours) by Call Source

Source: Author's own elaboration

Interpretation of Severity by Department in Colombia

This map illustrates the distribution of suicide attempt severity by poisoning across Colombian departments. Severe cases (yellow) are concentrated in departments such as Antioquia, Caldas, Meta, Nariño. In the other hand, moderate cases (orange) predominate across much of the territory, suggesting that the majority of intoxications are presented with clinically significant but non-fatal severity. Continuing, Mild cases (purple) are observed in central and northern departments, including Magdalena, Bolivar, Norte de Santander, Risaralda y Guaviare. Finally, there are no *fatal* cases (dark blue) reported. Departments in gray are labeled *NA*, which indicates “Not Applicable,” meaning no information on severity was recorded for those regions or that cases could not be classified into any of the available categories.

Figure 6 Interpretation of Severity by Department in Colombia

Source: Author's own elaboration

Substance involved

The 15 most common substances described in the overall case reports: acetaminophen, amitriptyline, quetiapine, sertraline, clonazepam, zopiclone, non-classified, fluoxetine, trazodone, tramadol, carbamazepine, escitalopram, levomepromazine, ibuprofen, risperidone.

Table 3 15 most common substances

Drug	Frequency
Acetaminophen	1302
Amitriptyline	985

Quetiapine	624
Sertraline	568
Clonazepam	564
Zopiclone	558
Non-classified	400
Fluoxetine	397
Trazodone	349
Tramadol	331
Carbamazepine	303
Escitalopram	261
Levopromazine	241
Ibuprofen	221
Risperidone	202

Source: Author's own elaboration

Discussion

In this study we conducted a secondary analysis of suicidal attempt in Colombia from the past 5 years with a large national database. We found that most cases took place in 2023, with a total of 4658 case reports; this data agrees with the information provided by the Legal Medicine And Forensic Sciences Institute (2), nonetheless, it rejects one of the hypotheses we initially proposed, where we stated that most cases may be seen in the years where the COVID pandemic took place. On the other hand, young adults were the most affected population group, where the median did not pass 24 years; this information also agrees with previous national data reports, in which the most affected age group was between 20-24 years. According to Tomaszek et al. in their study from Krakow, Poland in 2024, poisoning was the leading cause of suicide attempt in adolescents (16), sharing this conclusion with Fogaça et al. in their study from São Paulo, Brazil (17). Within our investigation we identified that Q1 in mild and moderate cases from both sexes were adolescents, while in severe cases, this behavior was seen primarily in females, whereas the masculine population showed a high heterogeneity in severe cases; these results support our second hypothesis, where we stated young adulthood was the most affected.

As it was previously mentioned, the majority of suicide cases in Colombia from 2023 were executed by men, still, we identified a gender preponderance, with 14702 (73.05%) of suicide attempts accounted to women. In addition, it was also stated in the Polish study previously mentioned that antidepressants, antipsychotics and acetaminophen constituted the most common substances used for suicide attempts (16), while in the study of Namkee, et al. from United States, they described antidepressants, benzodiazepines, cardiovascular drugs and opioids as the most used medications in suicide attempts (18); partly coinciding with our findings, where the most frequently

used substance was acetaminophen, followed by amitriptyline and quetiapine, supporting the third hypothesis raised. Acetaminophen is one of the most widely used medications worldwide, used as an analgesic and antipyretic (20), offering an effective, rapid and straightforward pain management, as it doesn't need medical prescription for its purchase and can be easily found in most pharmacies, revealing that accessibility could account as the main causality factor that conditions why most intoxication cases were caused by the overdose of this medication. On the other hand, the second most used substances in suicidal intoxication were psychiatric medications, such as antidepressants and antipsychotics, an observation that may indicate a baseline mental health condition and thus, attribute a higher risk of suicide attempts. It is important to note that all poisonings were by oral route.

Now, observing time between event and report all groups had a high variability, except response team, in which the time registered was 0.87 hours. Forwardly, we noticed that calls from medical centers were the ones presenting the longest time, with an average of 59.78 hours, stating a significant delay in reports. Individual reports were also presented with high times, which could possibly indicate difficulty in access. Finally, according to the Forensics report of 2023, the areas hosting the majority of cases were Antioquia (562), Bogotá D.C. (439), Valle del Cauca (270), Cundinamarca (179) and Nariño (123) (2), where this results could be partly intertwined with the ones from our study, which showed most severe cases in Antioquia, Nariño, Meta and Caldas, while Bogotá D.C. and Valle Del Cauca had moderate cases. The majority of cases were reported in urban areas compared to rural regions. Further analysis is needed to determine whether this disparity reflects limited accessibility and underreporting, rather than an actual lower incidence in rural populations.

Conclusion

The characterization of intoxication related with suicidal behavior presented in this article captures the multiple risk factors that can be related to this growing public health issue, where, as we said previously, young, productive population are the most affected, establishing the need to promote interdisciplinary work throughout health and political systems. We must also acknowledge and correct the prolonged times between the time of the event and report, reducing possible difficulties in access. The results obtained show an underlying social problematic, where public awareness campaigns are advised in order to prevent, diagnose and treat accordingly the fundamental origin of suicide attempts. We vigorously encourage keeping up with epidemiological vigilance of this matter, establishing routes to a better, healthier and happier society.

Limitations

The use of secondary health surveillance data is subject to limitations caused by deficiencies in reporting quality, including underreporting and the absence of relevant clinical variables in some reports.

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Appendices:

Table 1. Operational Definitions of Study Variables (adapted from the Cisproquim database, administered by the Colombian Security Council (CCS) (11)).

Variable	Description	Variable Type	Measuring Scale	Role in Analysis
Age	Age of individual at the time of suicide attempt.	Quantitative	Continuous (years); grouped categories	Independent variable; used for stratification.
Sex	Biological sex recorded in Cisproquim.	Qualitative	Nominal (Male/Female)	Independent variable; sociodemographic characterization.
Region of Residence	Administrative region and rural/urban classification.	Qualitative	Nominal (Andean, Caribbean, Pacific, etc.; Urban/Rural)	Independent variable; spatial distribution.
Substance Involved	Main toxic substance used in the suicidal intoxication.	Qualitative	Nominal (20 most frequent substances + others)	Independent variable; epidemiological characterization.
Severity of Case	Clinical severity classification of intoxication.	Qualitative	Ordinal (Mild, Moderate, Severe, Fatal)	Dependent variable; outcome indicator.
Outcome	Final clinical result of the intoxication event.	Qualitative	Nominal (Recovery, Sequelae, Death)	Dependent variable; main outcome.
Year of Event	Year in which the case was reported to Cisproquim.	Quantitative	Discrete (2019–2024)	Independent variable; temporal trend analysis.
Route of Administration	Pathway of exposure to toxic substance.	Qualitative	Nominal (Oral, Parenteral,	Independent variable;

			Inhalation, Other)	descriptive variable.
Time to Notification	Interval between event and case notification to Cisproquim.	Quantitative	Continuous (hours); grouped ($\leq 24h$, $25-72h$, $>72h$)	Independent variable; surveillance process assessment.
Primary Care Level	Healthcare service level where the case was first attended.	Qualitative	Nominal (Primary, Secondary, Tertiary)	Independent variable; healthcare system characterization.
Intent	Classification of poisoning intent.	Qualitative	Nominal (Suicidal)	Inclusion criterion; ensures case selection.

Information provided by the Colombian Security Council 2019-2024

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